

Development of Business Plan for Sustainable Turnkey Solar Panel Production Factory

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Abstract: As the global demand for renewable energy sources continues to rise, solar power stands out as a prominent and sustainable energy solution. The paper presents development of comprehensive business plan for establishment of turnkey solar panel production factory with a strong focus on sustainability and environmental responsibility. The paper aims at addressing the growing market demand for high-quality solar panels while minimizing its environmental footprint and contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. The business plan outlines key factors necessary for successful establishment and operation of solar panel production factory, including market analysis, financial projections, operational strategies, and sustainability initiatives. Market analysis through examination of the global trends in solar energy market, identifying growth trends, potential competitors, and target customer segments. Result show that a payback period of 16 months and break-even point of 30,112 units. The financial projections outlined the investment requirements, revenue forecasts, and profitability expectations for the proposed factory. In conclusion, the research paper presents a well-structured business plan for the establishment of a turnkey solar panel production factory that not only meets the ever-increasing demand for solar energy solutions but also prioritizes sustainability and environmental responsibility. The renewable energy solution provided by this paper offers a compelling opportunity for investors, aligning financial growth with a positive impact by providing clean and reliable energy solutions to a growing global market. The use of eco-friendly manufacturing processes, utilization of recyclable materials, and adoption of energy-efficient technologies to minimize its carbon footprint is recommended.

Keywords: Footprint; Carbon; Eco-Friendly; Greenhouse Gas; Well-Structured; Emissions; Turnkey; and Sustainable.

Introduction

Electricity is a critical enabler and an indispensable commodity which is required for the economic growth and development of any nation, Tuballa and Abundo (2016). Energy is an asset as well as a resource for mankind without which human survival will be impossible, Poizot and Dolhem, (2011). The industrial growth of any country is determined by the availability and efficient utilization of energy resources, Tuballa and Abundo (2016). Human existence and survival depend largely on the quality, quantity, availability and cost of energy

Energy is required for various industrial processes such as heating steam, firing of furnaces and petroleum refining processes, metal working and manufacturing processes (Kumar et al., 2023; Hdom and Fuinhas, 2020; Holechek et al., 2022). At the domestic level, different sources of energy are used for cooking, laundry, running TV sets, musical systems, lightings, boiling and space heating. Transportation of human beings, equipment, raw materials, finished goods from one place to another is solely dependent on availability and consumption of energy which is in different forms, ranging from solar, liquid fossil fuel, compressed natural gas, coal, wind, thermal, hydro-dynamic energy and shale oil (Rödger *et al.*, 2021). In Nigeria for example, in spite of recent reforms in the energy sector,

the challenges ahead are tremendous (Ayamolowo *et al.*, 2022). Recent estimates have shown that to achieve the vision 2050 goal of making Nigeria one of the twenty largest economies in the world, electricity generation will have to increase from the present level of 5000 MW to about 45000 MW or even more (Bamisile *et al.*, 2021) . The shortage of electricity supply is of great concern in Nigeria despite considerable quantity of available renewable and non-renewable energy resources (Opeyemi, 2021).

Electricity is an essential input to the growth and development of the various sectors of the economy (Toman and Jemelkova, 2003; Wolde-Rufael, 2006; Suganthi and Samuel, 2012; Osueke and Ezugwu, 2011). Thus, an increase in electricity production is an indication of economic growth. A large chunk of the electricity generated in Nigeria comes from the burning of fossil fuels (coal, oil and gas) which accounts for high percent of greenhouse gas emissions and contributes significantly to climate change (Osueke and Ezugwu, 2011; Shaaban and Petinrin, 2014). Hence, there is a critical need for transition from fossil fuel dependent energy production to renewable energy sources. Scientific literature has made it very clear that to avoid the worst impacts of climate change, emissions need to be reduced by almost half by 2030 and reach near zero by 2050

(Shaaban and Petinrin (2014). To achieve this, there is need to put an end to over reliance on fossil fuels and invest more in alternative sources of energy that are clean, accessible, affordable, sustainable and reliable (Diesendorf, 2022; Rabbi *et al.*, 2022).

Solar energy is the radiant light and heat from the Sun that is harnessed using a wide range of technologies such as solar panels to generate electricity, solar thermal energy (including solar water heating systems), and solar architecture (Oyedepo, 2014). Solar energy is an essential source of renewable energy, and its technologies are broadly characterized as either passive solar or active solar depending on how they capture and distribute solar energy or convert it into solar power (Kasimova *et al.*, 2023). Active solar techniques include the use of photovoltaic systems, concentrated solar power, and solar water heating to harness the energy (Bosu *et al.*, 2023).

The background of solar energy can be traced back to ancient times, when people used sunlight to heat their homes and cook their food (Ahmed *et al.*, 2021). In the 17th century, the first solar-powered steam engine was invented (Kumar *et al.*, (2023). However, it wasn't until the 20th century that solar energy began to be developed as a viable source of electricity (Babu *et al.*, 2023). In 1954, the first silicon solar cell was developed, which was capable of converting sunlight into

electricity at an efficiency of 6%, (Matakane *et al.*, 2023). Since then, the efficiency of solar cells has improved dramatically, and the cost of solar panels has fallen significantly (Matakane *et al.*, 2023). Today, solar energy is one of the fastest-growing sources of energy in the world (Patnaik *et al.*, (2020). In the year 2021, solar power accounted for 10% of global electricity generation (Lu *et al.*, 2021; Kruitwagen *et al.*, 2021). This is expected to increase to 20% by 2030 and 30% by 2040 (Obaideen *et al.*, 2021). Solar energy is significant because it is a renewable, clean, and abundant source of energy (Obaideen *et al.*, 2021). The significance of solar energy is growing as we become more aware of the need to transition to clean energy sources, (Przychodzen and Przychodzen, 2020). Solar energy is a key part of the potential solution to climate change and other environmental challenges (Omri and Belaïd, 2021). Electricity generation from solar energy can help to reduce our reliance on fossil fuels, which are a major source of greenhouse gas emissions (Omri and Belaïd, 2021). Solar energy can also help to improve energy security and reduce air pollution (Omri and Belaïd, 2021). According to Omri and Belaïd (2021), some of the key benefits of solar energy to mankind include:

- Solar energy is a renewable resource, which means that we will never run out of it.

- Solar energy does not produce any greenhouse gas emissions or other pollutants.
- Solar energy is the most abundant source of energy on Earth.
- Solar energy can be used to generate electricity, heat water, and power homes and businesses.
- The cost of solar panels has fallen dramatically in recent years, making solar energy a more affordable energy source than ever before.

The solar energy industry has experienced remarkable growth and transformation in recent years, driven by advancements in technology, environmental concerns, innovation, and growing focus on sustainability, energy transition, and economic factors (Su and Fan, 2022; Bogdanov *et al.*, (2021). Solar energy industry encompasses development, manufacturing, installation, and maintenance of solar energy systems (Mastrocinque *et al.*, 2020). Solar energy industry includes a wide range of companies, from small startups to large multinational corporations (Mastrocinque *et al.*, 2020). The solar industry is on a trajectory for further expansion and integration into global energy systems, contributing to efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and combat climate change. The solar energy industry is divided into two main segments: photovoltaic (PV)

and concentrated solar power (CSP) (Sharma *et al.*, 2022). The photovoltaic technologies convert sunlight directly into electricity using solar cells while CSP technologies use mirrors to concentrate sunlight onto a receiver, which heats up a fluid that is then used to generate electricity (Sharma *et al.*, 2022). The PV segment is the larger and more mature of the two solar energy segments (Otamendi *et al.*, 2021). In 2022, PV accounted for over 90% of all new solar energy installations across the globe (Li *et al.*, 2022). Whereas the concentrated solar power (CSP) technologies are still in their early stages of development, but with potential to play a significant role in the future of solar energy (Li *et al.*, 2022).

Solar panel production industry is influenced by various factors like: government policies, energy market dynamics, and technological breakthroughs (Ding *et al.*, 2020). Since conditions in Solar panel production industry can change rapidly, it's advisable to consult the latest market reports and industry analyses for the most up-to-date information on market trends and growth projections in the solar panel production sector before committing ones capital into (Lan, 2023; Xin-gang *et al.*, 2021).. According to (Hermle *et al.*, 2020), Solar panel production market is expected to still grow significantly in the coming years, driven by a number of factors, including: (1) The cost of solar panels has fallen dramatically in recent years, making solar energy a more affordable energy source than

ever before; (2) Many governments around the world ready to provide financial incentives to promote the use of solar energy; (3) As people become more aware of the environmental impacts of fossil fuels, they are increasingly turning to solar energy as a clean and sustainable alternative; and (4) There is a growing demand for renewable energy sources as countries around the world seek to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions and transition to a clean energy future.

In a report by Allied Market Research, the global solar panel production market is expected to grow from \$152.3 billion in 2022 to \$330.4 billion by 2032, at a CAGR of 8.1% from 2023 to 2032, (Srivastava, 2022). The Asia-Pacific region is expected to be the largest market for solar panel production, followed by North America and Europe (Dudin *et al.*, 2019). The growth of solar panel production market in the Asia-Pacific region is attributed to factors such as increasing government support for solar energy, growing demand for electricity, and favorable climatic conditions (Bulturbayevich *et al.*, 2023). Presently the major players in the solar panel production market include: Trina Solar; Canadian Solar; Jinko Solar; JA Solar Technology; and Yingli Solar (Feldman *et al.*, 2021). These companies are continuously investing heavily into new production capacity and facilities to meet the growing demand for solar panels (Feldman *et al.*, 2021). The solar panel production market

is a dynamic and exciting sector with a bright future (Dehshiri *et al.*, 2023). As the cost of solar panels continues to decline and governments around the world continue to support its development, we can expect to see solar panel production grow significantly in the coming years (Dehshiri *et al.*, 2023). According to (Benda and Černá (2020); and (Pulli *et al.*, 2020), the following are some of the key trends in global solar panel production market: (1) Larger solar panels are becoming more popular because they offer a number of advantages, such as lower installation costs and higher efficiency (2) Development of new solar technologies, such as perovskite solar cells and bifacial solar panels, are being developed all the time (these new technologies have the potential to further reduce the cost and improve the efficiency of solar panels); and (3) Integration of solar panel production with other industries: Solar panel production is increasingly being integrated with other industries, such as the automotive industry. This is helping to reduce the cost and improve the availability of solar panels as well as economy of scale.

Sustainable practices in solar panel manufacturing are essential for minimizing the environmental impact of producing solar panels and ensuring that the overall life cycle of solar systems is environmentally responsible, (Tawalbeh *et al.*, 2021). Sustainability in solar panel manufacturing not only reduces the environmental footprint

of the industry but also enhances the long-term viability and acceptance of solar energy as a clean and responsible energy source (Butt *et al.*, 2022) and (Li and Huang, 2020). Manufacturers, policymakers, and consumers all have a role to play in promoting sustainable practices in solar panel production, (Li *et al.*, 2023). According to Abdou, Hassan and El-Dief (2020), there are a number of sustainable practices that solar panel manufacturers can implement to reduce the environmental impact of their operations. Some of these key practices include: (1) using recycled materials: Solar panel manufacturers can use recycled materials in their products, such as recycled silicon and aluminum (This helps to reduce the need to extract and process new raw materials); (2) solar panel manufacturers can use renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, to power their operations as opposed to fossil fueled powered system. This helps to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions; (3) solar panel manufacturing can be a highly water-intensive process. Solar panel manufacturers can reduce their water consumption by using water-efficient manufacturing processes and recycling water whenever possible; (4) reducing waste: Solar panel manufacturers can reduce their waste by implementing waste minimization and recycling programs. This helps to reduce the amount of waste that goes to landfills; (5) improving energy efficiency: Solar panel manufacturers can improve the

energy efficiency of their operations by upgrading their equipment and processes. This helps to reduce their energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions; (6) use lead-free solder: Lead is a toxic metal that can be harmful to the environment and human health. Solar panel manufacturers can use lead-free solder in their products to reduce the negative environmental impact of their products; (7) use non-toxic chemicals: Some of the chemicals used in solar panel manufacturing can be toxic to the environment and human health. Solar panel manufacturers can use non-toxic chemicals in their products to reduce the negative environmental impact of their products; and (8) Design for recyclability: Solar panel manufacturers can design their products to be more easily recycled. This helps to reduce the amount of waste that goes to landfills viz-a-viz environmental pollution.

A number of solar panel manufacturers have started implementing sustainable practices in their operations (Woodhouse *et al.*, 2019). For example, the solar panel manufacturer “Sun Power limited” has committed to using 100% renewable energy to power its operations by 2025, (Woodhouse *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, the solar panel manufacturer “First Solar” has committed to recycling 100% of its solar panels at the end of their life, (Woodhouse *et al.*, 2019). The implementation of sustainable practices by solar panel manufacturers is essential to reducing the environmental

impact of the solar energy industry (Woodhouse et al., 2019). As the solar energy industry continues to grow, it is important for solar panel manufacturers to continue to adopt sustainable practices to ensure that the industry remains sustainable in the long term, Woodhouse *et al.*, (2019). From the reviewed literature, it was observed that not much had been reported in the areas of combined production of solar panels plus storage batteries and inverter charging system together in one facility which is a gap in current knowledge. This knowledge gap necessitated the study. This research paper aims to provide a comprehensive and well-researched business plan for the establishment of a sustainable solar panel production factory, addressing financial, environmental, and market aspects. The findings will contribute to the broader discussion on renewable energy and sustainable manufacturing practices universally. The objective of the research paper is to develop a comprehensive and well-researched plan for the establishment and operation of a successful solar panel manufacturing business that is committed to sustainability and economic viability of the business for the investors. The outcome of this research paper will be informative and useful to entrepreneurs, investors, other stakeholders, and the general public with respect to sustainable solar panel production. The paper will also provide a clear and concise overview of the solar panel market,

the business model for the new solar panel manufacturing factory, and the company's sustainability plan.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Materials used for the study include: Camera; Calculator; Field note and pen; bill of engineering measurement and evaluation of a solar panel production factory; Laptop; and Microsoft excel software.

Methods

The study was carried out using a five steps methodology proposed by Adigio and Ohwofadjeke (2016) as follows;

Step 1: Intensive literature

Intensive literature search was carried out to identify gaps in current knowledge on solar panel production necessitating the study to completely define research problem/needs.

Step 2: Development Business plan

This step considered: market analysis/research; competitive analysis; marketing plan; operations plan; management team; and **funding**; financial projections and economic viability analysis.

Step 3: Data collection

Relevant Cost data were extracted from “the bill of engineering measurement and evaluation (BEME)” of a solar panel

production factory being the primary source of data for the research.

Step 4: Data classification and analysis:

Collected data organized and classified. Analysis of data was carried out using payback period method and breakeven point of the solar panel production factory considered.

Step 5: Writing and publication of final report/paper

Results of Financial Analysis

The financial analysis was carried out on the estimated project cost and revenue. The Most important parameter to execute a sustainable project of this nature (magnitude) is the cost and its return/recovery period. Having an in-depth understanding of financial analysis is primary to the implementation and success of the proposed factory plan.

Payback period Analysis for the proposed sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory

Payback period analysis component of the project financial analysis consist of the *construction cost* (fixed cost) and raw material cost (variable cost) and expected revenue. It is noteworthy that for the purpose of this economic analysis; 1\$ = ₦920. the financial analysis is examined as follow:

The cost of raw materials that will service the factory for thirty days production

Plus 2½% likely price fluctuations in raw material (variable cost) = ₦15,323,069.825

$$\text{Monthly operating cost} = \text{₦ } 612922793 + \text{₦ } 15,323,069.825 = \text{₦ } 628,245,862.825$$

Initial capital required for investment = Fixed cost + total operating cost for the first month

$$= \text{₦ } 1,369,052,052.8 + \text{₦ } 628,245,862.825$$

$$= \text{₦ } 1,997,297,915.625$$

Annual cost (first year) = Fixed cost + (monthly operating cost * 12) [1]

$$= 1,369,052,052.8 + (628,245,862.825 * 12)$$

$$= 1,369,052,052.8 + 7,538,950,353.9$$

$$= \text{₦ } 8,908,002,406.7$$

Expected Revenue (return on investment)

The factory will produce 16 solar panels/hour of 550W capacity each, and the factory proposes to run three shifts daily (24hours), each of 8 hours;

The factory will produce 384 panels/day of 550W capacity; which translates to 11,520 panels/month

From the foregoing, the factory will produce 138,240 solar panels/year

The selling price of 550W capacity solar panels in Nigeria is ₦100,000 per piece @ July 2023.

Hence; expected daily sales/production of ₦38,400,000,

Which will translate to ₦ 1,152,000,000 monthly,

Yearly expected sales = ₦ 13,824,000,000

Monthly expected revenue = value of total monthly production output – (total monthly operating cost) = ₦ 1,152,000,000 – ₦ 628,245,862.825 = ₦ 523,754,137.175

Yearly expected revenue = value of total monthly production output – (total monthly operating cost * 12) [2]

Yearly expected revenue = ₦ 523,754,137.175 * 12 = ₦ 6,285,049,646

The feasibility analysis was done using payback period (PBP) as follows:

$$PBP = \frac{\text{Initial investment Cost}}{\text{Cash Inflow}} \quad [3]$$

$$PBP = \frac{8,908,002,406.7}{6,285,049,646} = 1.4$$

Therefore, the estimated time to recover initial capital on investment is one year and four months (16 months).

Table 1 Summary of Financial Analysis

S/N	Financial component description	Amount (₦)
1.	Construction Cost (Fixed cost)	1,369,052,052.8
2.	Monthly operating cost	628,245,862.825
3.	Total annual operating cost (variable cost)	7,538,950,353.9
4.	Annual cost for first year	8,908,002,406.7
5.	Value of expected daily sales/production	38,400,000
6.	Value of expected monthly sales/production	1,152,000,000
7.	Value of Yearly expected sales	13,824,000,000
8.	Projected daily profit/benefit	17,219,314
9.	Projected Monthly profit/benefit	523,754,137.175
10.	Projected Yearly profit/benefit	6,285,049,646
11.	Initial capital required for investment	1,997,297,915

Note: 1\$ = ₦920

The Initial capital required for this investment is ₦ 1,997,297,915 (one billion, nine hundred and ninety-seven million, two hundred and ninety-seven thousand, nine hundred and fifteen Naira only).

Break Even Analysis for the proposed sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory

The breakeven point for the proposed “sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory” is the point where the total revenue generated from the sales of solar panels is equal to the total costs incurred in producing

and selling such products. To calculate the breakeven point, we need to know the following in each case:

- i. The fixed costs: These are the costs that are incurred regardless of the level of production, such as rent, salaries, and utilities.
- ii. The variable costs: These are the costs that vary directly with the level of production, such as the cost of cassava, labor, and packaging.
- iii. The selling price per unit of solar panel.

The breakeven point of the proposed ‘sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory’ can be calculated using the formula as follows;

$$\text{Breakeven point} = \text{Fixed costs} / (\text{Selling price per unit} - \text{Variable cost per unit}).$$

[4]

The following information were determined above:

- i. Fixed costs = 1,369,052,052.8
- ii. Variable costs per unit = $7,538,950,353.9 \div 138,240$
= 54,535.23
- iii. Selling price per unit = $13,824,000,000 \div 138,240$
= ₦ 100,000

$$\text{Contribution margin} = \text{Selling price per unit} - \text{Variable costs per unit}$$

[5]

$$\text{Contribution margin} = 100,000 - 54,535.23 = 45,464.77$$

Hence, the breakeven point is calculated as follows:

$$1,369,052,052.8 (100,000 - 54,535.23)$$

$$\text{Breakeven Point} = 1,369,052,052.8 \div 45,464.77$$

$$= 30,112 \text{ units (solar panels).}$$

The breakeven point of the proposed “sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory” is 30,112 units (solar panels).

Management of the proposed Factory

The factory would be managed by a Managing Director and guided by the board of Directors, whose nature, composition and functions would be towards the effective and smooth running of the proposed factory. The board of Directors shall have close working relationship with the factory Managing Director and management team on such issues as operation, programs, management and finances/Budget. The organogram for the proposed solar panel production factory is presented below in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Organizational structure of proposed turnkey solar panels production factory

Discussion

The Initial capital required for this investment is ₦ 1,997,297,915 (One Billion, Nine Hundred and Ninety-Seven Million, Two Hundred and Ninety Seven Thousand, Nine Hundred and Fifteen Naira only). The proposed “sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory” has one year and four months (16 months) estimated time to recovery of the initial capital on investment, with a breakeven point of 30,112 units (solar panels). This means that Solar Panel production factory must produce and sell a, minimum of 30,112 units of solar panels) in order to recover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 30,112 units (solar panels), it will make a profit. However, If the factory sells less than 30,112 units (solar panels), it

will make a loss. From the financial analysis, the initial capital that will be invested to establish the proposed solar panel production factory can be recovered in about one year and four months (16 months). The general rule of thumb for business feasibility assessment considers business ventures with less than three years capital recovery period to be viable.

Conclusion

The solar energy manufacturing industry is one of the fastest-growing industries in the world, and the demand for solar panels is expected to continue to grow in the coming years. This presents a significant opportunity for businesses that are able to produce high-quality solar panels in a sustainable and cost-effective manner. This research paper has

developed a comprehensive business plan for a sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory that covers all aspects of the business, from the conception, market survey and then to financial projections and viability analysis. The research paper has explored the intricacies of developing a comprehensive business plan for establishing a sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory. Through a thorough analysis of market trends, technological advancements, regulatory frameworks, and sustainability considerations, several key findings and insights have emerged as follows: (1) Establishing a solar panel production factory can create numerous job opportunities for local residents. These jobs may range from manufacturing and assembly positions to management, research and development, and administrative roles. This can help reduce unemployment rates and improve the economic well-being of the community; (2) the factory can provide training and skills development programs for local workers. Employees may acquire specialized skills in manufacturing, quality control, and renewable energy technology, which can be valuable for their long-term career prospects; (3) the factory may source materials and services locally. This can stimulate growth in local businesses, such as suppliers of raw materials, logistics, transportation, and maintenance services; Others are (4) the factory's presence can lead to an increase in tax revenue for the local

government. This additional revenue can be invested in public services, infrastructure improvements, and community development projects; (6) Solar panel production factories often engage with the local community through outreach programs, educational initiatives, and partnerships with local schools and universities. This can promote awareness of renewable energy, sustainability, and environmental stewardship; (7) Solar panels themselves have a positive environmental impact by reducing the community's carbon footprint and dependence on fossil fuels. A factory committed to sustainability may also implement green practices, such as using renewable energy sources, recycling, and reducing waste; (8) some solar panel factories engage in research and development activities. This can attract researchers, engineers, and innovators to the community, fostering a culture of innovation and potentially leading to new technologies and products; (9) Companies often invest in community initiatives and charitable activities. This can include donations to local charities, support for community events, and participation in local philanthropic efforts; (10) The presence of a sustainable solar panel factory can enhance the reputation of the community. This, in turn, may lead to an increase in property values as people are attracted to live in environmentally conscious and economically prosperous areas; (11) By producing solar panels locally, the community

may become more energy-independent, relying less on external sources of energy. This can provide stability in energy supply and reduce vulnerability to energy price fluctuations; (12) Residents often take pride in knowing that their community is contributing to a sustainable future through the production of clean energy technology which can boost morale and community cohesion; and (13) The presence of a solar panel production factory can diversify the local economy, reducing dependence on a single industry. This diversification can make the community more resilient to economic downturns in other sectors.

In light of these findings, it is evident that the development of a business plan for a sustainable turnkey solar panel production factory is not only a financially viable endeavor but also contributes significantly to the global transition towards clean and sustainable energy sources. This research serves as a valuable resource for entrepreneurs, investors, and policymakers interested in fostering the growth of the renewable energy sector. As we move forward, it is imperative for stakeholders to collaborate, innovate, and invest in renewable energy solutions to address the challenges of climate change and energy sustainability. The successful establishment of such a factory has the potential to not only drive economic growth but also reduce greenhouse gas emissions and promote a greener and more

sustainable future for generations to come. From the foregoing; therefore, the establishment of the proposed solar panel production factory is feasible and viable from environmental, economic and technical stand point. The proposed solar panel production factory is a promising investment with great benefits to the country's economy and attractive services to mankind and financier alike.

In conclusion, the path to a sustainable future begins with initiatives like the one explored in this research paper— a strong commitment to harnessing the power of the sun to meet our day-to-day energy needs while preserving the planet for future generations.

Recommendations

Based upon the findings of this paper, the author proposes the following recommendations:

1. The company should conduct regular market research to continuously identify the specific needs of its target market and improve solar panels that meet those needs so as to remain relevant and be in competitive advantage in solar panel production.
2. The company continuously develop and improve on its strong brand and identity marketing strategy to distinguish itself from its co-competitors.

3. The company should invest into constant research and development to continuously develop new and innovative solar panel technologies.
4. The company should partner with other organizations in the solar energy industry to share resources and expertise in areas that will be mutually beneficial to all the partners.
5. The company should strictly implement the comprehensive sustainability plan that outlined above, its goals and strategies for reducing environmental impact of its operation.

Finally, by adherence to the recommendations proposed above, the proposed factory stands high chances of having successful and sustainable turnkey solar panel production system/facility that will play a major role in meeting the ever growing demand of solar energy need for mankind and economic benefits for its investor (s).

Nomenclatures

Symbols

\$	=	United States Dollar
₦	=	Nigerian Naira
PBP	=	payback period
BEP	=	breakeven point

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